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Research Article

Quality Effectiveness Assessment Study On Different Brands Of Paracetamol Tablet Available In Navsari Market

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ABSTRACT

Drugs are any substance either biological or chemical and when consumed affects the physiological function of the body. These drugs are classified as OTC drugs or Prescription drugs. Both OTC drugs and Prescription drugs are available as Generic drugs or Branded/Proprietary drugs. While Branded drugs are protected by a patent for a particular number of years, generic drugs are not. Generic drugs only have to meet the same bio-equivalence requirement as their branded counterparts. Also, Branded drugs take a lot of time to get approved while generic drugs take a much lesser time. Due to the time taken for the Branded drugs to get approved, the costs used in the development of the drug, branded drugs then to get very expensive in the market while generic drugs are cheaper. We use authorized generic products, which are identical in composition and appearance to brand name products but are marketed as generic, as a control group to address this bias in an evaluation aiming to compare the effectiveness of generic versus brand medication.

INTRODUCTION

Paracetamol called acetaminophen or 4-acetamidophenol, is a common pain reliever and fever reduction medicine¹. Its chemical name is N-acetyl-p-aminophenol with a chemical formula C₈H₉NO₂. Paracetamol was first prepared in 1878 by Harmon Northrop Morse an American chemist². It is available as a generic medication with trade names including Tylenol and Panadol,

among others³. It is often sold in the commercial markets with a major ingredient in many cold and flu remedial combination drugs. It is usually used either by mouth or rectally, but is also available intravenously^{1,4}. Paracetamol is accessible in as a tablet, drops, capsules, injection, and syrup⁵. Paracetamol is usually safe at suggested doses.. The suggested maximum daily dosage for an adult is 3 or 4 grams^{7,8}. Higher doses may result in

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toxicity, including liver disaster. Serious skin rashes may infrequently occur, and it appears to be secure during pregnancy and breastfeeding

OVER THE COUNTER DRUGS:

Over the Counter Drugs are also called Non-Prescription drugs are drugs that are usually sold over the counter without a doctor's prescription. Over the counter drugs can be analgesics, NSAIDs, decongestants, antacids, anti-fungal drugs, cough suppressants (e.g anti-tussives and expectorants), anti-acne drugs, some topical antibiotics (usually available in the form of creams, ointments, powder, sprays, etc.

GENERIC DRUGS

Generic drug refers to the chemical composition of a drug and not the innovator drug which has a brand name in which the chemical composition of the drug is sold. It is usually identical as a proprietary drug in dose, potency, route of administration, quality, its action and does the same work as the drug was manufactured for. The term, generic, when used to describe household items implies that the item is cheaper and can be less effective and a duplicate version of a brand name product. But in the case of generic drugs, they are of the same quality and are as effective as that of the branded counterpart. The generic name is the name for the active pharmaceutical ingredient that is responsible for the therapeutic action and is found in the medicine that has been made. In other words, the generic name of a drug is the official name of a drug. It contains Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients same as the original brand name formulation. Generic drugs usually become available after the patent protection to the original developer of a drug expires. Pharmaceutical Ingredients such as demulscents, suspending agents, etc. That do not disturb the body to cure illnesses and may be different in physical appearance and shape. Paracetamol/Acetaminophen is the non-proprietary name(generic name) of Paracetamol drug.

BRANDED DRUGS/PROPIETARY DRUGS:

Proprietary drug is a drug that has a trade name and is protected by a patent (means that a drug can be manufactured and sold by the innovator company). A patent is given because pharmaceutical organisation spends lots of money and resources to make, develop and discover a new drug substance and hence they are given the exclusive rights to make and dispense the medicine for a particular duration. At the time of the patent protection, only the innovator company can make the drug and this is the reason a lot of people trust and know the proprietary

METHODOLOGY

Procedure:

- Weigh and powder 20 tablets.
- Take a quantity of the powder equivalent to 0.15 g of paracetamol 20 tablets $0.5g \text{ paracetamol wt } 0.15 \text{ g paracetamol} \rightarrow X$
- Place in a volumetric flask (200ml)
- Add 50 ml 0.1 M NaOH (using a burette)
- Dilute with 100 ml of water, shake for 15 minutes, and add sufficient water to produce 200 ml. Mix, and filter.
- Dilute 10 ml of the filtrate to 100 ml with water (in a volumetric flask 100ml).
- Add 10ml of the resulting solution to 10 ml of 0.1 M NaOH, dilute to 100 ml with
- water (in a volumetric flask 100ml)
- Measure the absorbance of the resulting solution at max 257 nm taking 0.715 as the value of Ers

Blank:

- Take 20 ml of 0.1 M NaOH and complete to 100 ml with water

Limit:

Content: 95-105% of the prescribed (labeled) amount.

RESULT

Brand	Batch no.	Price/10tab
Dolo	B1542	10.59
Calpol	5427	10.26
Cipla	1128	9.55
Generic	D25	7.45
API	--	--

Code	Name	Dosage	Manufacturer
01	Dolo	500 Mg	Micro
02	Calpol	500mg	Gsk
03	Paracip	500mg	Cipla
04	Generic	500mg	Jan Ausadhi
05	API	Q.S	-

ASSAY OF PCM

Name	Sample	Absorbance	Percentage Purity	Lambda
Dolo	A	0.262	101%	257nm
Calpol	B	0.263	100.9%	257nm
Cipla	C	0.279	101.7%	257nm
Generic	D	0.246	99.5%	257nm
API	E	0.279	101.2%	257nm

PARACETAMOL CALIBRATION CURVE

Paracetamol Calibration Curve

CONCLUSION:

This study showed the consumers general view and the reality of locally manufactured paracetamol tablet effectiveness. As the finding of the current study, consumers hold a negative view of the local paracetamol and tend to use the expensive brand paracetamol even though the laboratory specifications of the paracetamol tablet have met the standard. This study will be a benchmark for future studies, and further knowledge research should be done to access the knowledge and attitude of consumers and healthcare professionals on generic medicines to unveil the consumers practice and healthcare professional attitude. In the comparative analysis of generic drugs over the proprietary drugs, the analysis were made based on how they were developed. Proprietary drugs take lots of time to get approved as the new substance drug undergoes lots of testings (pre clinical as well as clinical testings). Also, the analysis was made based on the costs. Branded drugs are more expensive as seen in the cost estimate above. Generic drugs are cheaper option especially for long term treatments.

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